

THE CONTENT OF THE CURRICULUM OF ARABIC LANGUAGE OF THE ARABIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF BRUNEI DARUSSALAM: CLASS ELEVEN AS A CASE STUDY

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Abstract:

This research aims to identify the content of curriculum of Arabic Language in Brunei Arabic Secondary Schools in which Class Eleven was the case study. The researchers distributed questionnaires to four Arabic teachers who teach Arabic therein. After obtaining the data needed by the research, the researchers analyzed it descriptively and quantitatively in order to achieve the required objectives. The research outcome shows that most of the teaching content of class eleven is in line with the aims and objective of the curriculum, matches the students' language skills, takes cognizance of individual differences and contains the four Language skills, although some of them do not match their ages.

Keywords: curriculum of Arabic, Arabic secondary schools

1. Introduction

Teaching Arabic language in Brunei Darussalam soon had a significant amount of development in the sixties of the previous century, when regular Arabic schools for boys and girls were set up, when His Majesty Sultan (Haji 'Omar Sayf al-Din Sa'd al-KhairWa al-Din) laid the first foundation stone of Arab schools in the country on the day Thursday 17 of May in 1384 AH, corresponding to 24 September 1964, and then "Institute of Religious Teachers of Sri Begawan" (KUPUSB) opened in 1972 to produce the teachers of

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Arabic language and religious materials in religious primary schools. The establishment of these Arabian schools in Brunei Darussalam is counted one of the important scientific, religious and educational achievements, according to the results given as the great religious and educational goals achieved by these schools in Arab-Islamic aspects, as these schools play an important role in the formation of an educated Muslim society. These Arabic schools have become a basic important center for Islamic teaching (Shamsuddin and Sara: 2017).

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Content of Curriculum of Arabic Language in the Light of Modern Trend

Arabic Language Teaching Procedure in the light of current trends has outstepped from traditional concept which was based on instructive dictation to the learner as immensely spotted in the available theoretical knowledge characterized with the demands for restitution during examinations, to a teaching method in which student is supposed to acquire ability on how to successfully utilize and employ knowledge in the various communicative stances.

For Arabic Language to attain the realization of that effort, its teaching must necessarily be based on an accurate projection which can take the necessity in compliance with the modern inlets into consideration in language teaching and learning, and which can select the appropriate introduction for the nature of Arabic Language and the characteristics of its teaching and learning, in view of the fact that teaching access is the pivot in which the philosophy of Arabic Language is being crystallized. Also, it is expected that the principles of the formation of the linguistic program, content arrangement, fixation of appropriate teaching methods, teaching aids and evaluation systems together with means should be fixed through it in order to ensure the success of the teaching and learning procedure (Haniyyah 'Areef and Labukh Bujmaleen: 2015).

According to Abu Laban (2011), the content of the language textbook in the light of communicative approach is divided into two divisions:

- Cultural Content; it contains cultural subject matters from which the offering of language content is accomplishable.
- Linguistic Content; which contains Arabic Language Arts skills (Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing).

There are many criteria for the selection of the lively and communicative situations such as the followings:

- Realism: it implies possibility of its occurrence in the life of learner.
- Value: it indicates concordance and conformity of the situations, devices and activities with moral and religious domain for the society.
- Honesty and suitability: it means suitability of the situation or activity with its occasion and expression for what it represents.

- Efficacy: it means the extent of the expressions and effects of the situation in the future, the consequence of that stance is the availability reality and value. Therefore, the availability of these standards is an imperative matter, for the purpose of explicitness to the researchers and designers of books and textbooks of Arabic language. The linguistic communicative approach emphasizes on the fact that language teaching is perfectible within its application in the real functions. Meanwhile, mankind exploits language; so as to present himself or demand something or apologize for something, or accept or reject or exhibit his opinion on a specific issue.

Haafiz Ismail Alawi (2009) recounted a dialogue held with Daud Abduh where he defined the functional approach in Arabic Language Teaching in his statement that functional approach in Arabic Teaching is the Arabic teaching through the method that can lead to the mastery of the four language skills: Language comprehension audibly and visually, verbal and written expressions. Therefore, the function of language; whatever language it may be, is the ability on comprehensive understanding and instructiveness. And for the proficiency of these four skills, it is compulsory to give consideration to language grammatical principles (Morphological principles, syntactical principles and writing principles) as the means for the mastery of the previous four skills, no limits to it intrinsically.

It also requires the presence of an integration among linguistic specializations, psychology, sociology and pedagogy because the process of the teaching content selection is influenced by many factors which are partially connected with material things, and partially with the learner, in addition to the external factors which are envisaged in the teaching objectives, level of the curriculum and the fixed time. As these yardsticks and conditions were unavailable in our courses, students started linking the problems of Arabic Language Teaching with the failure of those in charge of the teaching syllabus in the selection of the appropriate linguistic content, especially on the issue of the selection of grammatical content which is considered as the main cause of students estrangement and renunciation from it (Abduh Ar-Raajih, 1995).

Ali Ahmad Madkur (2001) stated that the selection of grammatical subject courses for various classes in our schools can never be perfected on thematic basis, rather topics may be mostly selected based on the personal experience and subjective survey of the members of the curriculum creating committees.

Antwan Sayyaah (2014) added-when he was discussing the causes of the weakness of the Arabic Language Learners in syntax- saying that the weakness stemmed from the mixture of the meagreness of the grammatical subjects with its corpulence and the applied with the unreal forsaken subjects. Nowadays, we still have many textbooks full of inapplicable issues and subjects which cannot increase in the expressive competence of the student like those topics discussing the uses of: *Karuba, Haraa, Ikhlawlaqa* (from among the associates of *Kaada*), as well as persistency in the elaboration on the reasons for the indeclinable grammatical form (*Al-Mamnu'u minas Sarf*). Likewise, those books

are full of overproduction of the grammatical conditions and rules in respect of the *indeclinable grammatical form* in spite of its being a specific language or dialect, with the permissible removal of the preventability in the indeclinable grammar while it is impermissible to prevent the changeable form of it.

Mahmoud Ahmad As-Sayyid (1989) also viewed that the teaching of all of these issues without selection for content, or with the random selection of its subject courses, overburdens the student who can attain from his acquisitive intellectual ability for the Arabic Language principles which may lead to the reluctance of the students from such study and thereby increase in the aggravation of the phenomenon of linguistic weakness in the stage of general and university teaching.

Jaahiz (2000) also called for the satisfaction with the grammatical principles of language which can safeguard accurate communication and protect the tongues of speakers from grammatical mistake and error. On that, Jaahiz was saying in the chapter of „Baby Exercise“: *„As for the grammar, do not engage his heart with it, except in accordance with what can trigger him into safety from unreasonable mistake, and from the scope of the ignorance of the general public while writing a write up, composing a poem and describing anything else. Whatever is added on that, he is supposedly busy with better task and dumbfounded about the worst“*.

Nihaad Al-Musa (2015) brought an idea on the grammatical level, that we are in need of a device to distinguish the theoretical principles which can describe the phenomenon in the language course only, and abolish the theories of „causes“, „interpretations“ and „variations“, then come up with such principles on the grammatical fundamentals on which the grammarians unanimously agreed upon. Even the grammatical theories should be restricted from common principles among the grammarians, to those principles which have major roles in use and connected life in application. If we do this, we shall discover that grammar has been reduced into tenths to us, while every reader of this grammar will positively feel that he is truly reading something that has functional reflection near to what he is reading, hearing and what he is required to express.

Surely, the adoption of the functional way in Arabic Language Teaching necessitates the fact-findings of social situations to which mankind are subjected and in which he needs the use of language, its limitation, specification of the common use, classification of the terms, adaptation of its application in the class by the students and adjustment of the curriculum vocabularies so as to conform with the requirements of the situation. We are not obliged to teach everything to student in a way that he will not comprehend anything at the end; because the mastery of knowledge cannot be evaluated through the memorization of its rules, rather it is measurable through the ability on its usage and application.

However, it is necessary to point out that the functionality is not connected with issues of syntax, morphology, dictation and rhetoric only, but rather the issue is also connected with the selection of the subject matters which student needs at every stage

and which can expressively illustrate his interests and various demands, in addition to the evaluation matter and linguistic exercises. Thus, the adherence to the functional approach in the Arabic Language Teaching in our educational curriculums is an obligatory and important matter, but the most important is that such adherence must emanate from a conscious plan to the descriptive dimensions of the language, wherein the linguistic chapters which are majorly in use and circulation would be awarded a high position in the pedagogical programs. We must also concentrate on evaluative styles which can reap the student with ability on exploitation and application of language in various situations; we should eventually achieve a fruitful means for the language, not a preservative device only.

Henceforth, Arabic Language Learning and Teaching in line with the functional approach vividly makes the learning environment more smoothly harmonious with reality, as it often motivates the student and prompts him to learning. It eventually makes him more interested in the language for knowing its value and services which it offers to him in his life, because it is the ideal track which can enable him to face various situations in which the student might be in need of the particular language (Haniyyah Areef and Labukh Bujmaleen, 2015).

3. Research Methodology

This research is descriptive and quantitative. The researchers distributed questionnaires to four teachers, who teach Arabic in Class Eleven in the Brunei Arabic Secondary Schools. After getting the data required for the research, they analyzed it descriptively and quantitatively in order to required outcome.

3.1 The Content of the Curriculum of Arabic Language in the Class Eleven of Arabic Secondary Schools of Brunei

First: Curriculum content for teaching Arabic Language in Class Eleven in Brunei Arabic Secondary School conforms to the aims of the curriculum.

Table 1: Content of the curriculum agrees with the objectives

It is clear from the table that 50% of population agrees the Arabic Teaching syllabus of the class eleven of the Brunei Arabic secondary School matches the curriculum content 25% of the population neither agrees nor disagrees while the other 25% takes the opposite opinion that is, it does not agree with curriculum objectives. This shows that most of the Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven under study agrees with the curriculum objectives.

Second: The extent of agreement of the class eleven Arabic Secondary School with the age of the students.

Table 2: Agreement of the teaching syllabus with the age of students

It is clear from the table that 50% of the population agrees the content of the Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of Brunei Arabic Secondary school is suitable for the age of student while 50% are of the opposite opinion that is it is not suitable for their ages. This indicates that part of Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of the school under study is suitable for the age of the students while some other parts are not suitable for their ages.

Third: The extent of agreement of the Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of Brunei Arabic secondary school with students Language skills.

Table 3: Extent of Agreement of Arabic Teaching Syllabus with the students Language Level

It is clear from the table that 50% of the population agrees that the Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of Brunei Arabic Secondary school agrees with the students language level while 25% neither agrees or disagree while the other 25% are of opposite opinion that is it does not agree with the students language level this indicates that most of the Arabic Teaching Syllabus in class eleven of Arabic secondary school under study agrees with the student language.

Fourth: The extent of Correlation of Arabic Teaching Syllabus of Brunei Arabic Secondary School with Individual differences.

Table 4: Correlation of Arabic Teaching Syllabus with Students individual differences

It is clear from the table that 50% of the population agrees Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of Brunei Arabic Secondary School takes individual differences among students into consideration while the other 50% of population neither agrees nor disagrees. This shows that most of the Arabic teaching Syllabus of class eleven of the Arabic Secondary School under study takes individual differences among students into consideration.

Fifth: The extent of completeness of the Arabic teaching syllabus or class eleven of Brunei Arabic Secondary School with respect to the four Language Skills.

Table 5: The Arabic Teaching Syllabus contains the four languages skills

It is clear from the table above that 50% of the population agrees Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of the Brunei Arabic Secondary School contains the four language skill while 25% of them neither agree nor disagree and the other 25% takes the opposite opinion, that is, it does contain the four language skills.

4. Conclusion

The results of the research reveal that most of the contents of Arabic teaching syllabus of class eleven of Arabic Secondary Schools in Brunei Darussalam matches the aims and objectives, considers the students language skill, take cognizance of individual differences among the students and contains the four language skills, only that some of them do not match the age of the students.

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